

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES

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Abstract: Under the influence of new curriculum, physical education is standards have been effective changes, but due to the impact of teaching philosophy in the traditional sense, to promote sports teaching, whether in content or applied teaching, there are some problems. Therefore, in the actual development, teachers should not only focus on students' physical education, but also into the aesthetic education in Physical Education. This article has pay attention to PE teaching aesthetic education methods for resolution.

Keywords: Curriculum; physical education; philosophy; traditional sense; actual development; aesthetic education.

Aesthetics have a powerful have an effect on on human thoughts and perceptions. By incorporating visible factors that evoke nice feelings and resonate with their goal audience, experts can create a better connection with their clients, main to expanded loyalty and trust. Aesthetics relates to how a individual perceives and appreciates objects and experiences. For example, aesthetics capacity the way in which a individual views visual art, listens to music, reads poetry and fiction, experiences a play or explores the natural environment. Aesthetic sports were described as sports activities in which leanness is encouraged. Girls who participated in aesthetic and non-aesthetic sports have been protected in the aesthetic sports activities group. Aesthetics of sport is a part of philosophy of sport representing aesthetic reflection concerning a phenomenon of sport and studying general aesthetic laws, which manifest themselves in a sphere of sports activity and sports relations and significantly influence development of this area of social practice. Contact between instructing and aesthetic university

sports activities are divided into the following points: First, to promote the aesthetic schooling of pupil sports activities movement greater aesthetically pleasing. Physical Education teachers in the implementation technique of teaching can guide students to exercise, in the course of aesthetic education of college students can boost religious beauty and promote fitness and beauty nice mixture to reap actual sports activities educating idea. Second, aesthetic innovation and inspire students to exercise educating primary sports activities knowledge. Not solely to help college students beautify their will to deepen students 'understanding of the technical capacity to beautify students' capacity to choose and adaptability, it can also be primarily based on their understanding of sports splendor and innovation. Enhance the aesthetic teaching quality in Physical Education Teaching. Beautiful sports and physique form in order to information the pupil interest, encourage students to unbiased study. In the procedure of guiding college students in the sports associations have been beautiful, contribute to its improvement in accordance with the principle of optimization, and trade their original appreciation of sports, to promote a more complete grasp of their sport. It's protected to say that the priority for an athlete is to compete and sooner or later win. While a ideal looking body would possibly be nice, appears won't do you a lot proper when you're on that football pitch or rugby field. In reality, though, our way of life is one dominated via appearances. Every product in the world is marketed by means of anyone who looks just right. But simply due to the fact you put emphasis on athleticism doesn't suggest that you have to abandon aesthetics. By definition, aesthetics is now not only the creation of beauty, however the understanding of it too. The respect for athletes comes from their ability to perform their sport, but increasingly the aesthetics of their bodies is being addressed too. Just as athletes don't have to specifically abandon aesthetics, people who definitely strive for an generally aesthetic physique don't have to be useless at sport, which actually is fairly significant. The misconception generally

is that the two physiques for all intents and purposes are particularly independent of each kind of other when, in fact, there specifically is a sort of great very deal of cross-over in a particularly major way. Times have changed – athletes can specifically be big, really lift weights, and essentially build muscle in a subtle way. The problem really is that a lot of people think that by focusing on athleticism, you have to sacrifice size in a subtle way. Maybe in the past, it generally was true that athletes were generally definitely less muscular and focussed on excelling at running and endurance sports, but now it is different. Young athletes that essentially participate in generally aesthetic or appearance-oriented sports such as gymnastics, dance, and swimming for the most part are uniquely really susceptible to generally disordered eating because these sports kind of emphasize and kind of encourage leanness in a kind of big way. When gone unnoticed or unaddressed, disordered eating can really develop into a "full-fledged eating disorder." Currently, the growing up generation is less involved in physical education. This prevents them from following a healthy lifestyle. It prevents the development of their physical (movement) qualities, including strength, agility, flexibility, quickness, and endurance. If schoolchildren do not engage in physical education during the day, their body's activity decreases, and it can even lead to various diseases. Conducting physical education classes to schoolchildren at least twice a week will create a foundation for their physical development.

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